
WORK IN PROGRESS: PROPER AI/ML APPLICATION IN 6G NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

Although still in its early stages, 6G is expected to leverage Artificial Intelligence (AI)/Machine Learning (ML) methods to enable increasingly intelligent networks. The success of the next generation of mobile networks will largely depend on AI/ML-enabled mechanisms, making it essential to assess their application in this context.

This work focuses on evaluating how AI/ML has been applied in networking research through a set of well known Best Practices (BPs). The analysis was conducted on a large set of relevant research works, particularly recent 5G and Beyond Fifth-Generation Networks (B5G) research, as this is expected to set the groundwork for future 6G AI/ML.

The findings indicate that, in general, the maturity level of AI/ML applications in networking research is relatively low compared to other AI/ML applications. The considered BPs can serve as a crucial tool towards achieving reproducible, correct, and widely applicable AI/ML research for 6G, while also adhering to Open Science principles and strengthening its overall impact.

Keywords 6G · AI · ML · Best Practices · Intelligent Networks

1 Introduction

Communication trends are shifting towards a more advanced mobile system called 6G that prioritizes connected intelligence over people and things [1]. However, the anticipated features of 6G pose a challenge for traditional networking mechanisms. AI and ML techniques are promising alternatives to meet the stringent demands of 6G networks. Integration of AI and ML with communication systems is crucial and being recognized as important by 3GPP for both 5G and 6G systems [2, 3]. The upcoming generation of networks is predicted to rely heavily on AI/ML, which can analyze historical and contextual data and adapt to variable environments [4].

To ensure the development of effective and accurate AI/ML solutions for the next generation of networks, this study assesses the scientific maturity of proposed AI/ML applications for networks, focusing on 5G and B5G networks as they are latest tangible proposed solutions and the promising path for future networking systems. Since 6G is not yet defined, the study uses the term B5G to encompass both advanced 5G proposals and preliminary ideas for 6G networks.

To evaluate the maturity of AI/ML applications, a set of best practices (BPs) was gathered and 100 papers on 5G networks were screened. These BPs were collected from a similar study, although its scope was much broader.

The contribution of this work is an extensive analysis of the current state of compliance with common BPs in the field of networks. It is important to mention that this is preliminary work that will be further expanded in the future.

1.1 AI Best Practices

Starting a new AI project can be overwhelming due to the number of aspects to keep track of. Some researchers proposed BPs to avoid skipping critical steps in their research field. This subsection presents the BPs gathered from [5].

The BPs were grouped according to the typical AI pipeline presented in Figure 1. Given our focus on the research field, some BPs presented in [5] were left out, most related with privacy and teamwork, as these, although important, do not influence the pipeline and how the results are presented. The BP's grouping is presented in Table 1.

Figure 1: Standard AI pipeline.

Table 1: Best Practices from [5] grouped according to the AI pipeline.

AI pipeline section	Best Practices
Data collection	Use sanity checks for all external data sources; Check that input data is complete, balanced, and well distributed; Ensure data labeling is performed in a strictly controlled process.
Data transformation	Write reusable scripts for data cleaning and merging; Actively remove or archive features that are not used.
Task/Model Explanation	Share a clearly defined training objective within the team.
Model Training	Assign an owner to each feature and document its rationale; Automate hyperparameter optimization and model selection.
Model Evaluation	Test all feature extraction code; Peer review training scripts; Continuously measure model quality and performance; Capture the training objective in a metric that is easy to measure and understand.
Model Deployment	Share status and outcomes of experiments within the team; Enable parallel training experiments; Use versioning for data, models, configurations, and training scripts; Run automated regression tests; Use static analysis to check code quality; Use continuous integration; Enable shadow deployment; Log production predictions with the model's version and input data; Perform checks to detect skews between models; Automate model deployment; Enable automatic rollbacks for production models; Continuously monitor the behavior of deployed models.
Publishing	Make data sets available on shared infrastructure.
Outside the Scope	Enforce fairness and privacy Communicate, align and collaborate in multidisciplinary teams Work against a shared backlog Use a collaborative development platform

2 Current Status: AI/ML in Communications

This section presents how well the BPs is being followed in the area of telecommunications. For them we collected 100 publications using AI in 5G/B5G networks and analyzed their compliance with the defined BPs.

2.1 Research Methods

The well-known PRISMA [6] method was applied to review the relevant articles in the area. Many academic web search engines were used, namely: Google scholar¹, IEEE Xplore², Springer Link³, ACM digital library⁴, and Science Direct⁵.

In the first round of the search, keywords used were “AI”, “ML”, “5G”, and “Radio Access Network (RAN)”. But the returned papers were very general, introductory textbook level, and not really close to our field. Accordingly, it was found that we need to move to be more specific and define the borders of the research in the area of communication in 5G and beyond networks, where five traditional topics were selected regarding their functionalities and services in the field, namely: task offloading, resource allocation and management, spectrum management, channel estimation, and radio power management.

Based on the mentioned tags, keywords, and inquiries, about 20000 articles were found. From these articles, 100 papers were selected, which were chosen to cover a wide array of topics, to cover most of the applications and services based on ML solutions under the communication area in 5G and beyond networking.

The selected papers had to meet the following criteria:

- The research paper should be recent, published only in 2019 or after;
- The targeted area is 5G and B5G networks, in general, and the cellular access network in particular;
- The article addresses, develops, or proposes AI/ML techniques, algorithms, or methods of the critical problems in the 5G and B5G networks;
- The selected article clearly addresses the main identified problems in the field of 5G networks, besides mentioning the used ML algorithm to solve this problem;
- The proposed AI/ML algorithm is presented with (at least) minimal clarity with the necessary parameters, the used variables, and the initial values;
- The article is published in an academic journal with a good or high Impact Factor (more than 3.0) or presented at a high-class academic conference with core B or above, with more emphasis on journal articles, such as IEEE Transactions on Communications, IEEE Internet of Things Journal, Association for Computing Machinery (ACM), and Elsevier.

The chosen articles were diverse and addressed a wide range of network-related topics based on the functionalities of the papers, to study the compliance of each of them with the identified BP.

2.2 AI for Networks Landscape

Using the BPs described in subsection 1.1 and the 100 papers obtained with the research method described in the previous subsection, we can access the BPs’ compliance in 5G/B5G networks. These papers cover a wide range of AI models, including search and optimization techniques classified as traditional methods. Furthermore, there are also machine learning methods, which were divided into shallow and deep categories. The deep category is further divided into supervised, unsupervised, reinforcement learning, and a custom category for specialized methods. Figure 2 presents the full spectrum of observed AI models.

We devised a three-level scale to analyze the compliance of papers with the BPs. Papers were classified as compliant, non-compliant, or almost compliant, with corresponding numerical scores of 1, 0, and 0.5, respectively. For certain cases, such as in “Ensure data labeling is performed in a strictly controlled process” for Reinforcement Learning (RL) models, where a BP was not applicable, the paper is not considered and did not influence compliance metrics for that specific BP. Based on this, a high average compliance score (closer to 1) suggests that the 5G networks research field adheres closely to the BP, while a low average score (closer to 0) indicates a significant distance from compliance.

Our compliance analysis involves assessing the level of compliance with BP grouped by pipeline section across various networking tasks. The heat map in Figure 3 illustrates this information, with lighter tones indicating lower compliance and darker tones indicating better compliance. Upon initial inspection, it is apparent that many BPs exhibit low compliance. The heat map also reveals some variability between networking tasks, but the difference is not significant enough to conclude that one area is better than the other. Nonetheless, to evaluate telecommunications compliance

¹<https://scholar.google.com/>

²<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplore/home.jsp>

³<https://link.springer.com>

⁴<https://dl.acm.org/>

⁵<https://www.sciencedirect.com/>

Figure 2: Percentage of AI/ML algorithm types considered in the papers used for the analysis. Acronyms: SL(Supervised Learning), UL(Unsupervised Learning), RL(Reinforcement Learning), Custom(Algorithms combining different types of learning), and Traditional (Search and Optimization).

fairly, we should compare it with other areas using AI. To do so, we also presented the results obtained in [5] in this heat map. At first glance, in terms of following BPs and pursuing scientific correctness in the usage of AI/ML, B5G networks seem to be at a level comparable to general ML applications. It obtains better compliance in “Data Collection” and “Task/Model Explanation”, similar compliance in “Data Transformation” and “Model Evaluation”, and worst compliance in the remaining BPs.

However, some additional factors need to be taken into account. The papers considered in our analysis were published after 2019, while the study in [5] was finished in 2018. Besides, the study in [5] assessed industry projects and scientific research, having a much broader scope, with many considered items with less stringent quality objectives. Given that our study considers newer publications and a (not biased) much smaller scope, “similar compliance to AI BPs” is actually a negative assessment. The compliance in each stage was expected to be better than the general ML, given the different contexts of both studies. Besides, the BPs which present comparatively less compliance are critical for networks. For example, “Model Deployment” is a set of BPs that will ensure that the results presented in publications stay valid when the model is deployed. In some ML applications, the model is never expected to go into a production stage, so it is expected that the compliance would be low for such cases. However, in B5G networks, the models are usually presented as contributions to be applied in real production scenarios. The lack of compliance of these BPs when presenting these models can lead to a false sense of success, as the model can achieve good results, but the pipeline that ensures the results cannot be built.

Figure 3: BPs' compliance heatmap grouped by general task and AI pipeline stage comparing with General ML.

3 Conclusion

In the advent of the increasing entanglement of networking solutions and AI/ML mechanisms towards more intelligent networks, this document offered an analysis of the current state of the art AI/ML publications compliance with common BPs. This was achieved by defining 7 groups of BPs, and analyzing their compliance in 100 articles on the State-of-the-art (SOTA) of AI/ML in networking, specifically AI application B5G research.

The results of the statistical analysis of the study show that the progress of AI/ML in networks is mostly hampered by the lack of documentation in scientific publications, limiting users to reproducing or independently verifying published results and therefore to convert scientific innovation into technology. Comparison with other research fields suggests a similar trend, albeit worse in some aspects.

In general, the outcomes of this work can be seen as a warning improve research quality and ensure results' reproducibility. In fact, the results of this work could be leveraged not only by researchers but by all the different elements involved in the process of creating scientific knowledge and technologies.

References

- [1] Wen Tong and Peiyong Zhu. *6G, the Next Horizon: From Connected People and Things to Connected Intelligence*. Cambridge University Press, 2021.
- [2] Ali Nauman, Tu N. Nguyen, Yazdan A. Qadri, Zulqar Nain, Korhan Cengiz, and Sung Won Kim. Artificial intelligence in beyond 5g and 6g reliable communications. *IEEE Internet of Things Magazine*, 5(1):73–78, 2022.
- [3] 3GPP/Release 18. Rp-213602: Core part: Artificial intelligence (ai)/machine learning (ml) for ng-ran. Technical report, 3GPP, 2021.
- [4] Fadoua Debbabi, Rihab Jmal, and Lamia Chaari Fourati. 5g network slicing: Fundamental concepts, architectures, algorithmics, projects practices, and open issues. *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience*, page e6352, 2021.
- [5] Alex Serban, Koen van der Blom, Holger Hoos, and Joost Visser. Adoption and effects of software engineering best practices in machine learning. In *Proceedings of the 14th ACM/IEEE International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement (ESEM)*, pages 1–12, 2020.
- [6] Larissa Shamseer, David Moher, Mike Clarke, Davina Ghersi, Alessandro Liberati, Mark Petticrew, Paul Shekelle, and Lesley A Stewart. Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (prisma-p) 2015: elaboration and explanation. *Bmj*, 349, 2015.
- [7] Mu Yan, Gang Feng, Jianhong Zhou, Yao Sun, and Ying-Chang Liang. Intelligent resource scheduling for 5g radio access network slicing. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 68(8):7691–7703, 2019.
- [8] Yunzhao Li, Feng Qi, Zhili Wang, Xiuming Yu, and Sujie Shao. Distributed edge computing offloading algorithm based on deep reinforcement learning. *IEEE Access*, 8:85204–85215, 2020.
- [9] Adam A. Alli and Muhammad Mahbub Alam. Secoff-fciot: Machine learning based secure offloading in fog-cloud of things for smart city applications. *Internet of Things*, 7:100070, 2019.
- [10] Lingxia Wang, Chungang Yang, and Rose Qingyang Hu. Autonomous traffic offloading in heterogeneous ultra-dense networks using machine learning. *IEEE Wireless Communications*, 26(4):102–109, 2019.
- [11] Jiadai Wang, Lei Zhao, Jiajia Liu, and Nei Kato. Smart resource allocation for mobile edge computing: A deep reinforcement learning approach. *IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computing*, 9(3):1529–1541, 2021.
- [12] Jienan Chen, Siyu Chen, Qi Wang, Bin Cao, Gang Feng, and Jianhao Hu. iraf: A deep reinforcement learning approach for collaborative mobile edge computing iot networks. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 6(4):7011–7024, 2019.
- [13] Sheng Zhou, Yuxuan Sun, Zhiyuan Jiang, and Zhisheng Niu. Exploiting moving intelligence: Delay-optimized computation offloading in vehicular fog networks. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 57(5):49–55, 2019.
- [14] Dario Bega, Marco Gramaglia, Marco Fiore, Albert Banchs, and Xavier Costa-Pérez. Deepcog: Optimizing resource provisioning in network slicing with ai-based capacity forecasting. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 38(2):361–376, 2020.
- [15] Xiaosha Chen, Supeng Leng, Ke Zhang, and Kai Xiong. A machine-learning based time constrained resource allocation scheme for vehicular fog computing. *China Communications*, 16(11):29–41, 2019.

- [16] Jingci Luo, Jie Tang, Daniel K. C. So, Gaojie Chen, Kanapathippillai Cumanan, and Jonathon A. Chambers. A deep learning-based approach to power minimization in multi-carrier noma with swipt. *IEEE Access*, 7:17450–17460, 2019.
- [17] Hao Ye, Geoffrey Ye Li, and Biing-Hwang Fred Juang. Deep reinforcement learning based resource allocation for v2v communications. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 68(4):3163–3173, 2019.
- [18] Li-Chun Wang and Shao-Hung Cheng. Data-driven resource management for ultra-dense small cells: An affinity propagation clustering approach. *IEEE Transactions on Network Science and Engineering*, 6(3):267–279, 2019.
- [19] Zefeng Jia, Wenchi Cheng, and Hailin Zhang. A partial learning-based detection scheme for massive mimo. *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, 8(4):1137–1140, 2019.
- [20] Min Chen, Yiming Miao, Hamid Gharavi, Long Hu, and Iztok Humar. Intelligent traffic adaptive resource allocation for edge computing-based 5g networks. *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, 6(2):499–508, 2020.
- [21] Cheng Wu, Cheng Wang, Jie Sheng, and Yiming Wang. Cooperative learning for spectrum management in railway cognitive radio network. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 68(6):5809–5819, 2019.
- [22] Jun Liu, Kai Mei, Xiaochen Zhang, Dongtang Ma, and Jibo Wei. Online extreme learning machine-based channel estimation and equalization for ofdm systems. *IEEE Communications Letters*, 23(7):1276–1279, 2019.
- [23] Deliang Yi, Xin Zhou, Yonggang Wen, and Rui Tan. Efficient compute-intensive job allocation in data centers via deep reinforcement learning. *IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems*, 31(6):1474–1485, 2020.
- [24] Mukoe Cheong, Hyunsung Lee, Ikjun Yeom, and Honguk Woo. Scarl: Attentive reinforcement learning-based scheduling in a multi-resource heterogeneous cluster. *IEEE Access*, 7:153432–153444, 2019.
- [25] M. Shamim Hossain and Ghulam Muhammad. A deep-tree-model-based radio resource distribution for 5g networks. *IEEE Wireless Communications*, 27(1):62–67, 2020.
- [26] Changsung Lee, Hyoungjun Cho, Soeun Song, and Jong-Moon Chung. Prediction-based conditional handover for 5g mm-wave networks: A deep-learning approach. *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine*, 15(1):54–62, 2020.
- [27] Sahrish Khan Tayyaba, Hasan Ali Khattak, Ahmad Almogren, Munam Ali Shah, Ikram Ud Din, Ibrahim Alkhalifa, and Mohsen Guizani. 5g vehicular network resource management for improving radio access through machine learning. *IEEE Access*, 8:6792–6800, 2020.
- [28] G. M. Shafiqur Rahman, Tian Dang, and Manzoor Ahmed. Deep reinforcement learning based computation offloading and resource allocation for low-latency fog radio access networks. *Intelligent and Converged Networks*, 1(3):243–257, 2020.
- [29] Veeramanikandan, Suresh Sankaranarayanan, Joel J.P.C. Rodrigues, Vijayan Sugumaran, and Sergei Kozlov. Data flow and distributed deep neural network based low latency iot-edge computation model for big data environment. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 94:103785, 2020.
- [30] Mashael Khayyat, Ibrahim A. Elgendy, Ammar Muthanna, Abdullah S. Alshahrani, Soltan Alharbi, and Andrey Koucheryavy. Advanced deep learning-based computational offloading for multilevel vehicular edge-cloud computing networks. *IEEE Access*, 8:137052–137062, 2020.
- [31] Peng Yu, Fanqin Zhou, Xiang Zhang, Xuesong Qiu, Michel Kadoch, and Mohamed Cheriet. Deep learning-based resource allocation for 5g broadband tv service. *IEEE Transactions on Broadcasting*, 66(4):800–813, 2020.
- [32] Ying Chen, Zhiyong Liu, Yongchao Zhang, Yuan Wu, Xin Chen, and Lian Zhao. Deep reinforcement learning-based dynamic resource management for mobile edge computing in industrial internet of things. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, 17(7):4925–4934, 2021.
- [33] Arcangela Rago, Giuseppe Piro, Gennaro Boggia, and Paolo Dini. Multi-task learning at the mobile edge: An effective way to combine traffic classification and prediction. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 69(9):10362–10374, 2020.
- [34] Seung-Seob Lee and Sukyoung Lee. Resource allocation for vehicular fog computing using reinforcement learning combined with heuristic information. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 7(10):10450–10464, 2020.
- [35] Francesca Meneghello, Davide Cecchinato, and Michele Rossi. Mobility prediction via sequential learning for 5g mobile networks. In *2020 16th International Conference on Wireless and Mobile Computing, Networking and Communications (WiMob)*, pages 1–6, 2020.
- [36] Ruzat Ullah, Safdar Nawaz Khan Marwat, Arbab Masood Ahmad, Salman Ahmed, Abdul Hafeez, Tariq Kamal, and Muhammad Tufail. A machine learning approach for 5g sinr prediction. *Electronics*, 9(10), 2020.

- [37] Yu Chen, Jingya Zhao, Qinghua Zhu, and Yong Liu. Research on unlicensed spectrum access mechanism based on reinforcement learning in laa/wlan coexisting network. *Wireless Networks*, 26(3):1643–1651, Apr 2020.
- [38] Hyebin Park and Yujin Lim. Reinforcement learning for energy optimization with 5g communications in vehicular social networks. *Sensors*, 20(8), 2020.
- [39] Helin Yang, Xianzhong Xie, and Michel Kadoch. Machine learning techniques and a case study for intelligent wireless networks. *IEEE Network*, 34(3):208–215, 2020.
- [40] Ping Xiang, Hangguan Shan, Miao Wang, Zhiyu Xiang, and Zhenguo Zhu. Multi-agent rl enables decentralized spectrum access in vehicular networks. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 70(10):10750–10762, 2021.
- [41] Mehyar Najla, Zdenek Becvar, Pavel Mach, and David Gesbert. Predicting device-to-device channels from cellular channel measurements: A learning approach. *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, 19(11):7124–7138, 2020.
- [42] Ya Li, Xiaohui Zhao, and Hui Liang. Throughput maximization by deep reinforcement learning with energy cooperation for renewable ultradense iot networks. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 7(9):9091–9102, 2020.
- [43] Sihua Wang, Mingzhe Chen, Xuanlin Liu, Changchuan Yin, Shuguang Cui, and H. Vincent Poor. A machine learning approach for task and resource allocation in mobile-edge computing-based networks. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 8(3):1358–1372, 2021.
- [44] Yaser Azimi, Saleh Yousefi, Hashem Kalbkhani, and Thomas Kunz. Energy-efficient deep reinforcement learning assisted resource allocation for 5g-ran slicing. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 71(1):856–871, 2022.
- [45] Hasan Albinsaid, Keshav Singh, Sudip Biswas, Chih-Peng Li, and Mohamed-Slim Alouini. Block deep neural network-based signal detector for generalized spatial modulation. *IEEE Communications Letters*, 24(12):2775–2779, 2020.
- [46] Brijesh Soni, Dhaval K. Patel, and Miguel López-Benítez. Long short-term memory based spectrum sensing scheme for cognitive radio using primary activity statistics. *IEEE Access*, 8:97437–97451, 2020.
- [47] Wenyan Ma, Chenhao Qi, Zaichen Zhang, and Julian Cheng. Sparse channel estimation and hybrid precoding using deep learning for millimeter wave massive mimo. *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 68(5):2838–2849, 2020.
- [48] Bhekisizwe Mthethwa and Hongjun Xu. Deep learning-based wireless channel estimation for mimo uncoded space-time labeling diversity. *IEEE Access*, 8:224608–224620, 2020.
- [49] Xuemei Yi and Caijun Zhong. Deep learning for joint channel estimation and signal detection in ofdm systems. *IEEE Communications Letters*, 24(12):2780–2784, 2020.
- [50] Huaping Liu, Hyeonsung Kim, Sangmi Moon, and Intae Hwang. Deep learning for channel estimation and tracking in vehicular to infrastructure communications. In *2020 International Conference on Information and Communication Technology Convergence (ICTC)*, pages 777–782, 2020.
- [51] Xiuhong Wei, Chen Hu, and Linglong Dai. Deep learning for beamspace channel estimation in millimeter-wave massive mimo systems. *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 69(1):182–193, 2021.
- [52] Tianxiang Zhang, Yuxin Bian, Qianchun Lu, Jin Qi, Kai Zhang, Hong Ji, Wanyuan Wang, and Weiwei Wu. Supervised learning based resource allocation with network slicing. In *2020 Eighth International Conference on Advanced Cloud and Big Data (CBD)*, pages 25–30, 2020.
- [53] James Hall, Klaus Moessner, Richard MacKenzie, Francois Carrez, and Chuan Heng Foh. Dynamic scheduler management using deep learning. *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, 6(2):575–585, 2020.
- [54] Boris Galkin, Ramy Amer, Erika Fonseca, and Luiz A. DaSilva. Intelligent base station association for uav cellular users: A supervised learning approach. In *2020 IEEE 3rd 5G World Forum (5GWF)*, pages 383–388, 2020.
- [55] Hamid Shiri, Jihong Park, and Mehdi Bennis. Communication-efficient massive uav online path control: Federated learning meets mean-field game theory. *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 68(11):6840–6857, 2020.
- [56] Fan Meng, Peng Chen, Lenan Wu, and Julian Cheng. Power allocation in multi-user cellular networks: Deep reinforcement learning approaches. *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, 19(10):6255–6267, 2020.
- [57] Zhu Tianqing, Wei Zhou, Dayong Ye, Zishuo Cheng, and Jin Li. Resource allocation in iot edge computing via concurrent federated reinforcement learning. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 9(2):1414–1426, 2022.

- [58] Fan Jiang, Rongxin Ma, Youjun Gao, and Zesheng Gu. A reinforcement learning-based computing offloading and resource allocation scheme in f-ran. *EURASIP Journal on Advances in Signal Processing*, 2021(1):91, Oct 2021.
- [59] Umar Farooq, Muhammad Wasif Shabir, Muhammad Awais Javed, and Muhammad Imran. Intelligent energy prediction techniques for fog computing networks. *Applied Soft Computing*, 111:107682, 2021.
- [60] Qian You and Bing Tang. Efficient task offloading using particle swarm optimization algorithm in edge computing for industrial internet of things. *Journal of Cloud Computing*, 10(1):41, Jul 2021.
- [61] Feiyang Sun, Pinghui Wang, Junzhou Zhao, Nuo Xu, Juxiang Zeng, Jing Tao, Kaikai Song, Chao Deng, John C.S. Lui, and Xiaohong Guan. Mobile data traffic prediction by exploiting time-evolving user mobility patterns. *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, 21(12):4456–4470, 2022.
- [62] Kishor, Chinmay Chakraborty, and Wilson Jeberson. A novel fog computing approach for minimization of latency in healthcare using machine learning. *International Journal of Interactive Multimedia and Artificial Intelligence*, In Press:1, 01 2020.
- [63] Marcin Hoffmann and Pawel Kryszkiewicz. Reinforcement learning for energy-efficient 5g massive mimo: Intelligent antenna switching. *IEEE Access*, 9:130329–130339, 2021.
- [64] Fahime Khoramnejad and Melike Erol-Kantarci. On joint offloading and resource allocation: A double deep q-network approach. *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, 7(4):1126–1141, 2021.
- [65] Sharda Tripathi, Corrado Puligheddu, Carla Fabiana Chiasserini, and Federico Mungari. A context-aware radio resource management in heterogeneous virtual rans. *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, 8(1):321–334, 2022.
- [66] Yuansheng Wu, Guanqun Zhao, Dadong Ni, and Junyi Du. Dynamic handoff policy for ran slicing by exploiting deep reinforcement learning. *EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking*, 2021(1):61, Mar 2021.
- [67] Almuthanna Nassar and Yasin Yilmaz. Deep reinforcement learning for adaptive network slicing in 5g for intelligent vehicular systems and smart cities. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 9(1):222–235, 2022.
- [68] Marco Miozzo, Zoraze Ali, Lorenza Giupponi, and Paolo Dini. Distributed and multi-task learning at the edge for energy efficient radio access networks. *IEEE Access*, 9:12491–12505, 2021.
- [69] Aysenur Turkmen, Shuja Ansari, Paulo Valente Klaine, Lei Zhang, and Muhammad Ali Imran. Impress: Indoor mobility prediction framework for pre-emptive indoor-outdoor handover for mmwave networks. *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, 2:2714–2724, 2021.
- [70] Jie Mei, Xianbin Wang, Kan Zheng, Gary Boudreau, Akram Bin Sediq, and Hatem Abou-Zeid. Intelligent radio access network slicing for service provisioning in 6g: A hierarchical deep reinforcement learning approach. *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 69(9):6063–6078, 2021.
- [71] Ramesh Sekaran, Surya Narayana Goddumbarri, Suresh Kallam, Manikandan Ramachandran, Rizwan Patan, and Deepak Gupta. 5g integrated spectrum selection and spectrum access using ai-based frame work for iot based sensor networks. *Computer Networks*, 186:107649, 2021.
- [72] Ramsha Ahmed, Yueyun Chen, and Bilal Hassan. Deep learning-driven opportunistic spectrum access (osa) framework for cognitive 5g and beyond 5g (b5g) networks. *Ad Hoc Networks*, 123:102632, 2021.
- [73] Mauro Belgiovine, Kunal Sankhe, Carlos Bocanegra, Debashri Roy, and Kaushik R. Chowdhury. Deep learning at the edge for channel estimation in beyond-5g massive mimo. *IEEE Wireless Communications*, 28(2):19–25, 2021.
- [74] Kai Mei, Jun Liu, Xiaoying Zhang, Kuo Cao, Nandana Rajatheva, and Jibo Wei. A low complexity learning-based channel estimation for ofdm systems with online training. *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 69(10):6722–6733, 2021.
- [75] Zhiyuan Mai, Yueyun Chen, and Liping Du. A novel blind mmwave channel estimation algorithm based on ml-elm. *IEEE Communications Letters*, 25(5):1549–1553, 2021.
- [76] Ly V. Nguyen, A. Lee Swindlehurst, and Duy H. N. Nguyen. Svm-based channel estimation and data detection for one-bit massive mimo systems. *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, 69:2086–2099, 2021.
- [77] Zhen Chen, Jie Tang, Xiu Yin Zhang, Qingqing Wu, Yuxin Wang, Daniel K. C. So, Shi Jin, and Kai-Kit Wong. Offset learning based channel estimation for intelligent reflecting surface-assisted indoor communication. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, 16(1):41–55, 2022.
- [78] Youness Arjoun and Saleh Faruque. Experience-driven learning-based intelligent hybrid beamforming for massive mimo mmwave communications. *Physical Communication*, 51:101534, 2022.

- [79] Shuhao Xia, Yuanming Shi, Yong Zhou, and Xiaojun Yuan. Reconfigurable intelligent surface for massive connectivity: Joint activity detection and channel estimation. *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, 69:5693–5707, 2021.
- [80] Shuyi Shen, Ticao Zhang, Shiwen Mao, and Gee-Kung Chang. Drl-based channel and latency aware radio resource allocation for 5g service-oriented rrf-mmwave ran. *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, 39(18):5706–5714, 2021.
- [81] Junsheng Mu, Xiaojun Jing, Yangying Zhang, Yi Gong, Ronghui Zhang, and Fangpei Zhang. Machine learning-based 5g ran slicing for broadcasting services. *IEEE Transactions on Broadcasting*, 68(2):295–304, 2022.
- [82] Shahram Mollahasani, Melike Erol-Kantarci, and Rodney Wilson. Dynamic cu-du selection for resource allocation in o-ran using actor-critic learning. In *2021 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM)*, pages 1–6, 2021.
- [83] Weiting Zhang, Dong Yang, Haixia Peng, Wen Wu, Wei Quan, Hongke Zhang, and Xuemin Shen. Deep reinforcement learning based resource management for dnn inference in industrial iot. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 70(8):7605–7618, 2021.
- [84] Md. Sakir Hossain and Zdenek Becvar. Soft frequency reuse with allocation of resource plans based on machine learning in the networks with flying base stations. *IEEE Access*, 9:104887–104903, 2021.
- [85] Xiangnan Liu, Haijun Zhang, Keping Long, Arumugam Nallanathan, and Victor C. M. Leung. Energy efficient user association, resource allocation and caching deployment in fog radio access networks. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 71(2):1846–1856, 2022.
- [86] Ziyang Yang, Haibo Mei, Wenyong Wang, Dongdai Zhou, and Kun Yang. Joint resource allocation for emotional 5g iot systems using deep reinforcement learning. *International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics*, 12(12):3517–3528, Dec 2021.
- [87] Indranil Sarkar, Mainak Adhikari, Sanjay Kumar, and Varun G. Menon. Deep reinforcement learning for intelligent service provisioning in software-defined industrial fog networks. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 9(18):16953–16961, 2022.
- [88] Fatma M. Talaat, Hesham A. Ali, Mohamed S. Saraya, and Ahmed I. Saleh. Effective scheduling algorithm for load balancing in fog environment using cnn and mpso. *Knowledge and Information Systems*, 64(3):773–797, Mar 2022.
- [89] Nebojsa Bacanin, Milos Antonijevic, Timea Bezdan, Miodrag Zivkovic, K. Venkatachalam, and Sharaf Malebary. Energy efficient offloading mechanism using particle swarm optimization in 5g enabled edge nodes. *Cluster Computing*, 26(1):587–598, Feb 2023.
- [90] Jusik Yun, Yunyeong Goh, Wonsuk Yoo, and Jong-Moon Chung. 5g multi-rat urllc and embb dynamic task offloading with mec resource allocation using distributed deep reinforcement learning. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 9(20):20733–20749, 2022.
- [91] Youpeng Tu, Haiming Chen, Linjie Yan, and Xinyan Zhou. Task offloading based on lstm prediction and deep reinforcement learning for efficient edge computing in iot. *Future Internet*, 14(2), 2022.
- [92] Elham Karimi, Yuanzhu Chen, and Behzad Akbari. Task offloading in vehicular edge computing networks via deep reinforcement learning. *Computer Communications*, 189:193–204, 2022.
- [93] Parag Verma, Rajeev Tiwari, Wei-Chiang Hong, Shuchi Upadhyay, and Yi-Hsuan Yeh. Fetch: A deep learning-based fog computing and iot integrated environment for healthcare monitoring and diagnosis. *IEEE Access*, 10:12548–12563, 2022.
- [94] Chao Fang, Hang Xu, Yihui Yang, Zhaoming Hu, Shanshan Tu, Kaoru Ota, Zheng Yang, Mianxiong Dong, Zhu Han, F. Richard Yu, and Yunjie Liu. Deep-reinforcement-learning-based resource allocation for content distribution in fog radio access networks. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 9(18):16874–16883, 2022.
- [95] Xiaoyu Liu, Chi Xu, Haibin Yu, and Peng Zeng. Multi-agent deep reinforcement learning for end—edge orchestrated resource allocation in industrial wireless networks. *Frontiers of Information Technology & Electronic Engineering*, 23(1):47–60, Jan 2022.
- [96] Greta Vallero, Daniela Renga, Michela Meo, and Marco Ajmone Marsan. Ran energy efficiency and failure rate through ann traffic predictions processing. *Computer Communications*, 183:51–63, 2022.
- [97] Zhengguang Gao, Shuangyi Yan, Jiawei Zhang, Bingtao Han, Yongcheng Wang, Yuming Xiao, Dimitra Simeonidou, and Yuefeng Ji. Deep reinforcement learning-based policy for baseband function placement and routing of ran in 5g and beyond. *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, 40(2):470–480, 2022.

- [98] Junjie Cen and Yongbo Li. Resource allocation strategy using deep reinforcement learning in cloud-edge collaborative computing environment. *Mobile Information Systems*, 2022:9597429, Jul 2022.
- [99] Xuezhu Li. 5g converged network resource allocation strategy based on reinforcement learning in edge cloud computing environment. *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 2022:6174708, May 2022.
- [100] Muhammad Nauman Qureshi, Muhammad Khalil Shahid, Moazzam Islam Tiwana, Majed Haddad, Irfan Ahmed, and Tarig Faisal. Neural networks for energy-efficient self optimization of enodeb antenna tilt in 5g mobile network environments. *IEEE Access*, 10:61678–61694, 2022.
- [101] Yosvany Hervis Santana, Rodney Martinez Alonso, Glauco Guillen Nieto, Luc Martens, Wout Joseph, and David Plets. Indoor genetic algorithm-based 5g network planning using a machine learning model for path loss estimation. *Applied Sciences*, 12(8), 2022.
- [102] Iacovos Ioannou, Christophoros Christophorou, Vasos Vassiliou, and Andreas Pitsillides. A novel distributed ai framework with ml for d2d communication in 5g/6g networks. *Computer Networks*, 211:108987, 2022.
- [103] Fábio D.L. Coutinho, Hugerles S. Silva, Petia Georgieva, and Arnaldo S.R. Oliveira. 5g cascaded channel estimation using convolutional neural networks. *Digital Signal Processing*, 126:103483, 2022.
- [104] Herman Lucas dos Santos, José Carlos Marinello, Cristiano Magalhaes Panazio, and Taufik Abrão. Machine learning-aided pilot and power allocation in multi-cellular massive mimo networks. *Physical Communication*, 52:101646, 2022.
- [105] Mohammed S. Alzaidi, Chatti Subbalakshmi, T. V. Roshini, Piyush Kumar Shukla, Surendra Kumar Shukla, Papiya Dutta, and Musah Alhassan. 5g-telecommunication allocation network using iot enabled improved machine learning technique. *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, 2022:6229356, Jun 2022.

Appendix

Table 2: Full list of the datasets.

Ref	Name	Network operation	Year
[7]	Intelligent Resource Scheduling for 5G Radio Access Network Slicing	Task Offloading	2019
[8]	Distributed Edge Computing Offloading Algorithm Based on Deep Reinforcement Learning	Task Offloading	2019
[9]	SecOFF-FCIoT: Machine learning based secure offloading in Fog-Cloud of things for smart city applications	Task Offloading	2019
[10]	Autonomous Traffic Offloading in Heterogeneous Ultra-Dense Networks Using Machine Learning	Task Offloading	2019
[11]	Smart Resource Allocation for Mobile Edge Computing: A Deep Reinforcement Learning Approach	Resource allocation	2019
[12]	iRAF: A Deep Reinforcement Learning Approach for Collaborative Mobile Edge Computing IoT Networks	Resource allocation	2019
[13]	Exploiting Moving Intelligence: Delay-Optimized Computation Offloading in Vehicular Fog Networks	Resource allocation	2019
[14]	DeepCog: Optimizing Resource Provisioning in Network Slicing With AI-Based Capacity Forecasting	Resource allocation	2019
[15]	A machine-learning based time constrained resource allocation scheme for vehicular fog computing	Resource allocation	2019
[16]	A Deep Learning-Based Approach to Power Minimization in Multi-Carrier NOMA With SWIPT	Resource allocation	2019
[17]	Deep Reinforcement Learning Based Resource Allocation for V2V Communications	Spectrum Management	2019
[18]	Data-Driven Resource Management for Ultra-Dense Small Cells: An Affinity Propagation Clustering Approach	Spectrum Management	2019
[19]	A Partial Learning-Based Detection Scheme for Massive MIMO	Spectrum Management	2019
[20]	Intelligent Traffic Adaptive Resource Allocation for Edge Computing-based 5G Networks	Spectrum Management	2019
[21]	Cooperative Learning for Spectrum Management in Railway Cognitive Radio Network	Spectrum Management	2019

[22]	Online Extreme Learning Machine-Based Channel Estimation and Equalization for OFDM Systems	Channel estimation	2019
[23]	Efficient Compute-Intensive Job Allocation in Data Centers via Deep Reinforcement Learning	Task Offloading	2020
[24]	SCARL: Attentive Reinforcement Learning-Based Scheduling in a Multi-Resource Heterogeneous Cluster	Task Offloading	2020
[25]	A Deep-Tree-Model-Based Radio Resource Distribution for 5G Networks	Resource allocation	2020
[26]	Prediction-Based Conditional Handover for 5G mm-Wave Networks: A Deep-Learning Approach	Resource allocation	2020
[27]	5G Vehicular Network Resource Management for Improving Radio Access Through Machine Learning	Resource allocation	2020
[28]	Deep reinforcement learning based computation offloading and resource allocation for low-latency fog radio access networks	Resource allocation	2020
[29]	Data Flow and Distributed Deep Neural Network based low latency IoT-Edge computation model for big data environment	Resource allocation	2020
[30]	Advanced Deep Learning-Based Computational Offloading for Multilevel Vehicular Edge-Cloud Computing Networks	Resource allocation	2020
[31]	Deep Learning-Based Resource Allocation for 5G Broadband TV Service	Resource allocation	2020
[32]	Deep Reinforcement Learning-Based Dynamic Resource Management for Mobile Edge Computing in Industrial Internet of Things	Resource allocation	2020
[33]	Multi-Task Learning at the Mobile Edge: An Effective Way to Combine Traffic Classification and Prediction	Resource allocation	2020
[34]	Resource Allocation for Vehicular Fog Computing Using Reinforcement Learning Combined With Heuristic Information	Resource allocation	2020
[35]	Mobility Prediction via Sequential Learning for 5G Mobile Networks	Resource allocation	2020
[36]	A Machine Learning Approach for 5G SINR Prediction	Spectrum Management	2020
[37]	Research on unlicensed spectrum access mechanism based on reinforcement learning in LAA/WLAN coexisting network	Spectrum Management	2020
[38]	Reinforcement Learning for Energy Optimization with 5G Communications in Vehicular Social Networks	Spectrum Management	2020
[39]	Machine Learning Techniques and A Case Study for Intelligent Wireless Networks	Spectrum Management	2020
[40]	Multi-Agent RL Enables Decentralized Spectrum Access in Vehicular Networks	Spectrum Management	2020
[41]	Predicting Device-to-Device Channels From Cellular Channel Measurements: A Learning Approach	Spectrum Management	2020
[42]	Throughput Maximization by Deep Reinforcement Learning With Energy Cooperation for Renewable Ultradense IoT Networks	Spectrum Management	2020
[43]	A Machine Learning Approach for Task and Resource Allocation in Mobile-Edge Computing-Based Networks	Spectrum Management	2020
[44]	Energy-Efficient Deep Reinforcement Learning Assisted Resource Allocation for 5G-RAN Slicing	Spectrum Management	2020
[45]	Block Deep Neural Network-Based Signal Detector for Generalized Spatial Modulation	Spectrum Management	2020
[46]	Long Short-Term Memory Based Spectrum Sensing Scheme for Cognitive Radio Using Primary Activity Statistics	Spectrum Management	2020
[47]	Sparse Channel Estimation and Hybrid Precoding Using Deep Learning for Millimeter Wave Massive MIMO	Spectrum Management	2020
[48]	Deep Learning-Based Wireless Channel Estimation for MIMO Uncoded Space-Time Labeling Diversity	Channel estimation	2020
[49]	Deep Learning for Joint Channel Estimation and Signal Detection in OFDM Systems	Channel estimation	2020
[50]	Deep Learning for Channel Estimation and Tracking in Vehicular to Infrastructure Communications	Channel estimation	2020
[51]	Deep Learning for BeamSpace Channel Estimation in Millimeter-Wave Massive MIMO Systems	Channel estimation	2020
[52]	Supervised Learning Based Resource Allocation with Network Slicing	Wireless power management	2020

[53]	Dynamic Scheduler Management Using Deep Learning	Wireless power management	2020
[54]	Intelligent Base Station Association for UAV Cellular Users: A Supervised Learning Approach	Wireless power management	2020
[55]	Communication-Efficient Massive UAV Online Path Control: Federated Learning Meets Mean-Field Game Theory	Wireless power management	2020
[56]	Power Allocation in Multi-User Cellular Networks: Deep Reinforcement Learning Approaches	Wireless power management	2020
[57]	Resource Allocation in IoT Edge Computing via Concurrent Federated Reinforcement Learning	Task Offloading	2021
[58]	A reinforcement learning-based computing offloading and resource allocation scheme in F-RAN	Task Offloading	2021
[59]	Intelligent energy prediction techniques for fog computing networks	Task Offloading	2021
[60]	Efficient task offloading using particle swarm optimization algorithm in edge computing for industrial internet of things	Task Offloading	2021
[61]	Mobile Data Traffic Prediction by Exploiting Time-Evolving User Mobility Patterns	Resource allocation	2021
[62]	A Novel Fog Computing Approach for Minimization of Latency in Healthcare using Machine Learning	Resource allocation	2021
[63]	Reinforcement Learning for Energy-Efficient 5G Massive MIMO: Intelligent Antenna Switching	Resource allocation	2021
[64]	On Joint Offloading and Resource Allocation: A Double Deep Q-Network Approach	Resource allocation	2021
[65]	A Context-Aware Radio Resource Management in Heterogeneous Virtual RANs	Resource allocation	2021
[66]	Dynamic handoff policy for RAN slicing by exploiting deep reinforcement learning	Resource allocation	2021
[67]	Deep Reinforcement Learning for Adaptive Network Slicing in 5G for Intelligent Vehicular Systems and Smart Cities	Resource allocation	2021
[68]	Distributed and Multi-Task Learning at the Edge for Energy Efficient Radio Access Networks	Resource allocation	2021
[69]	IMPRESS: Indoor Mobility Prediction Framework for Pre-Emptive Indoor-Outdoor Handover for mmWave Networks	Resource allocation	2021
[70]	Intelligent Radio Access Network Slicing for Service Provisioning in 6G: A Hierarchical Deep Reinforcement Learning Approach	Spectrum Management	2021
[71]	5G Integrated Spectrum Selection and Spectrum Access using AI-based Framework for IoT based Sensor Networks	Spectrum Management	2021
[72]	Deep learning-driven opportunistic spectrum access (OSA) framework for cognitive 5G and beyond 5G (B5G) networks	Spectrum Management	2021
[73]	Deep Learning at the Edge for Channel Estimation in Beyond-5G Massive MIMO	Channel estimation	2021
[74]	A Low Complexity Learning-Based Channel Estimation for OFDM Systems With Online Training	Channel estimation	2021
[75]	A Novel Blind mmWave Channel Estimation Algorithm Based on ML-ELM	Channel estimation	2021
[76]	SVM-Based Channel Estimation and Data Detection for One-Bit Massive MIMO Systems	Channel estimation	2021
[77]	Offset Learning Based Channel Estimation for Intelligent Reflecting Surface-Assisted Indoor Communication	Channel estimation	2021
[78]	Experience-driven learning-based intelligent hybrid beamforming for massive MIMO mmWave communications	Channel estimation	2021
[79]	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface for Massive Connectivity: Joint Activity Detection and Channel Estimation	Channel estimation	2021
[80]	DRL-Based Channel and Latency Aware Radio Resource Allocation for 5G Service-Oriented RoF-MmWave RAN	Wireless power management	2021
[81]	Machine Learning-Based 5G RAN Slicing for Broadcasting Services	Wireless power management	2021
[82]	Dynamic CU-DU Selection for Resource Allocation in O-RAN Using Actor-Critic Learning	Wireless power management	2021

[83]	Deep Reinforcement Learning Based Resource Management for DNN Inference in Industrial IoT	Wireless power management	2021
[84]	Soft Frequency Reuse With Allocation of Resource Plans Based on Machine Learning in the Networks With Flying Base Stations	Wireless power management	2021
[85]	Energy Efficient User Association, Resource Allocation and Caching Deployment in Fog Radio Access Networks	Wireless power management	2021
[86]	Joint resource allocation for emotional 5G IoT systems using deep reinforcement learning	Wireless power management	2021
[87]	Deep Reinforcement Learning for Intelligent Service Provisioning in Software-Defined Industrial Fog Networks	Task Offloading	2022
[88]	Effective scheduling algorithm for load balancing in fog environment using CNN and MPSO	Task Offloading	2022
[89]	Energy efficient offloading mechanism using particle swarm optimization in 5G enabled edge nodes	Task Offloading	2022
[90]	5G Multi-RAT URLLC and eMBB Dynamic Task Offloading With MEC Resource Allocation Using Distributed Deep Reinforcement Learning	Task Offloading	2022
[91]	Task Offloading Based on LSTM Prediction and Deep Reinforcement Learning for Efficient Edge Computing in IoT	Task Offloading	2022
[92]	Task offloading in vehicular edge computing networks via deep reinforcement learning	Task Offloading	2022
[93]	FETCH: A Deep Learning-Based Fog Computing and IoT Integrated Environment for Healthcare Monitoring and Diagnosis	Resource allocation	2022
[94]	Deep-Reinforcement-Learning-Based Resource Allocation for Content Distribution in Fog Radio Access Networks	Resource allocation	2022
[95]	Multi-agent deep reinforcement learning for end—edge orchestrated resource allocation in industrial wireless networks	Resource allocation	2022
[96]	RAN energy efficiency and failure rate through ANN traffic predictions processing	Resource allocation	2022
[97]	Deep Reinforcement Learning-Based Policy for Baseband Function Placement and Routing of RAN in 5G and Beyond	Resource allocation	2022
[98]	Resource Allocation Strategy Using Deep Reinforcement Learning in Cloud-Edge Collaborative Computing Environment	Resource allocation	2022
[99]	5G Converged Network Resource Allocation Strategy Based on Reinforcement Learning in Edge Cloud Computing Environment	Resource allocation	2022
[100]	Neural Networks for Energy-Efficient Self Optimization of eNodeB Antenna Tilt in 5G Mobile Network Environments	Spectrum Management	2022
[101]	Indoor Genetic Algorithm-Based 5G Network Planning Using a Machine Learning Model for Path Loss Estimation	Spectrum Management	2022
[102]	A novel Distributed AI framework with ML for D2D communication in 5G/6G networks	Spectrum Management	2022
[103]	5G cascaded channel estimation using convolutional neural networks	Channel estimation	2022
[104]	Machine learning-aided pilot and power allocation in multi-cellular massive MIMO networks	Wireless power management	2022
[105]	5G-Telecommunication Allocation Network Using IoT Enabled Improved Machine Learning Technique	Wireless power management	2022